

High-frequency Titration Cells. Part I. Electrode Distance

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Influence of interelectrode separation on the high-frequency titrations at 6.47 megacycles has been studied. Results obtained have been explained with the help of the capacity changes in an equivalent parallel circuit.

The application of high-frequency oscillations proved useful in certain cases of titrations and chemical analyses. The idea was suggested by Blake¹ in 1937, but the work on this field really began after publication of Jensen and Parrack's investigations² in 1946. In this method the cell or a beaker containing the solution to be tested was placed in the tank coil of an anode circuit. Others arranged the cell between two metal sheets and connected it in parallel to the capacitor circuit. The electrodes being placed on the outside of the beaker do not come in direct contact with the solution inside. High-frequency method is thus not connected with the electrochemical changes taking place at the phase boundary of the solution-electrode system, but is connected with the electrochemical properties of the entire system between the electrodes. The response observed in this case is attributed to the rate of migration of ions and displacement of charge throughout the material and is directly or indirectly related to the dielectric and other electrical properties of the material to be tested. Measurements may therefore be regarded as a composite function of both the dielectric constant and the conductance of the sample and any system, which displays changes in one or both of these properties with alteration in composition, may be analysed by the application of this method.

Analysis is usually carried out by noting the changes produced with continued addition of a titrant and plotting these changes graphically. A break in the curve indicates the end point of the process going on. Geometry of the cell plays an important role in providing satisfactory response during titration. The various geometrical factors, such as, the thickness of the cell wall, area, and separation of electrodes from each other, should be taken into consideration in the design of a good titration cell. In the present communication the distance of electrode separation was specially studied with reference to the titration of dilute hydrochloric acid by an approximately twenty times stronger sodium hydroxide solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

The high-frequency apparatus used in the present investigation is a modification of that proposed by Hall³. The frequency of 6.475 megacycles per sec. was produced with the help of a Piezo-electric quartz crystal.

1. *J. Roy. Soc. Arts*, 1933, **82**, 154.
2. *Anal. Chem.*, 1946, **18**, 595.
3. *Ibid.*, 1952, **22**, 1244.

The titration cell, used herein, was a beaker made of Sigcol Indox (borosilicate) glass with walls having 2.3 mm thickness and 8.85 cm diameter with two electrodes made of copper ribbons, each 1 cm in breadth wound round it. It was connected in parallel with other capacitors in the circuit. The copper bands serving as electrodes could be separated, when necessary, by loosening screws fitted to them.

The chemical reaction studied was the neutralisation of dilute hydrochloric acid solution (0.00113*N*), kept in the titration cell, by a sodium hydroxide solution (0.024*N*), run down from a microburette. The change in capacitance in the circuit, brought about by the change in composition of the contained solution in course of titration, was compensated by a condenser, connected in parallel, in order to produce necessary oscillations of the crystal. Construction of the condenser was such that its capacity was linearly related to the dial reading, each of which corresponded to 1.0 picofarad.

The dial was also fitted with a vernier reading up to 1/10th of a division. The diminution of the capacitance of the solution needed an increase in that of the condenser to produce the necessary oscillations in the quartz crystal. Figs. 1 and 2 show the changes in capacitance of the solution, plotted in terms of the condenser dial readings.

DISCUSSION

Shape of the Titration Curve

The titration curve appears in Fig. 1 which resembles the conductometric titration curve in its general appearance. The capacity of the cell at first decreases with the addition of the base, but subsequently exhibits increase beyond the end point. The titration yielded results within 0.1% of an actual titration by use of indicators.

Foreman and Crisp⁴ concluded that ionic solutions were specially influenced by H.F. oscillations due to molecular polarisation. The electrolytic solution under such circumstances absorbs energy from the high-frequency field and the frequency is changed. Falkenhagen⁵ has shown that the frequency and concentration for maximum absorption are related to the time of relaxation of ions. For liquids with appreciable conductance, it may appear that absorption of energy is largely due to the motion of ions and hence its similarity with conventional conductometry⁶.

FIG. 1

4. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1946, **42A**, 186.

5. "Electrolytes", Oxford University Press, London, 1934.

6. Ewing, "Instrumental Methods of Chemical Analysis".

In the light of the above observations, it is easy to understand the downward run of the curve in the beginning (due to the replacement of faster moving hydrogen ions by comparatively sluggish Na^+ ions) and the subsequent rise beyond the end point.

Reilly and McCurdy⁷, working at different frequencies, obtained curves of different types, all of which did not correspond to the conventional conductometric curves. They were therefore of opinion that "all factors, which affect the low-frequency conductivity such as temperature, concentration of electrolyte, ionic mobility, degree of ionisation and other chemical factors which affect high frequency conductance, such as the operating frequency, dielectric constant of the solvent and cell constant, will combine to determine the shape of the high-frequency conductance titration curve". Because the same cell and the solvent are employed for all acid-base titrations, only the frequency and acid concentration need be considered as the most important determining factors.

Depth of the Titration Curve

The above workers are, however, silent regarding the influence which electrode distance plays in this case. It was, however, observed that the greater the depth of the titration curve (i.e. greater the changes in capacity produced in a given titration), the more pronounced would be the break and more accurate the result. But the change in capacitance appears not to depend on the difference in the ionic mobilities of the ions alone nor on the factors mentioned above. Other factors appear to be responsible for this. In the

FIG. 2

present case, it has been observed that the distance between electrodes plays a profound influence on the change in the capacitance in the titration cell. Our results on the study of the influence of electrode distance on the capacity changes in course of titration appear in Fig. 2 where changes in the dial readings, which represent changes in the capacitance of the circuit, during titration have been plotted against the distance between the two ribbons of copper used as electrodes.

Evidently, at low electrode distances, capacity changes during the titration were small, but the latter gradually increased with the electrode distance and reached a maximum constant value beyond a distance of about 3.5 cm between the electrodes. The titration curve presented in Fig. 1 represents the one when the electrode distance is kept at 4 cm. At lower distance the titration curve (not shown in figures) were less

satisfactory as the depths of the break were considerably less. With large distances up to 8 cm, as studied herein, no further advantage was gained.

This minimum inter-electrode distance of optimum performance (3.5 cm) in the present case has been found out here by the trial and error. Obviously, this does not depend on the conductance of the solution alone, in which case it would be the same for all electrode separations and the question of optimum separation would not arise. There are possibly other factors influencing this phenomenon, like the dielectric properties of the material of the containing vessel, its thickness, etc. which are being studied one by one.

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